

Assessment of Availability and Utilization of Information and Communication Technology Skills among Colleges of Education Students in North-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the availability and utilization of Information and Communication Technology Skills among Colleges of Education Students in North-West, Nigeria. A survey research design was adopted for the study. All students enrolled at Federal Colleges of Education in North-West, Nigeria during the 2021/2022 academic session made up the study's population. A random sample of 384 (243 male & 141 female) students were selected from the three Colleges chosen for this research. A validated questionnaire titled "Students ICT Skills Assessment Questionnaire (SICTSAQ)" was used for data collection. Reliability coefficient of 0.74 was obtained using Cronbach alpha reliability test. Mean, standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, t-test and ANOVA to test hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance, data analyses were explored using SPSS version 22.0. Results indicate that ICT facilities were moderately available in the Colleges (mean = 3.32), students possessed good ICT skills (mean = 3.48), the level of students' usage of ICT in learning was moderate (mean = 3.14), and there was no significant difference in the level of ICT skills obtained among male and female students ($P > 0.05$). The study concludes that there is a need for transformation of learning to continue when schools are closed due to any pandemic. Recommendations among others include Students enrolled in the Colleges of Education in North-West, Nigeria are encouraged to enhance their proficiency in ICT skills and effectively incorporate these abilities into their educational pursuits.

Keywords: Students, ICT, Skills, Availability, Utilization.

Introduction

Knowledge and skills are required by digital-age students for the optimal use of Information and Communication Technology for learning. These students thrive on creative and engaging activities from diverse sources of information from the digital world. This ability can be harnessed for digital learning. Digital learning can take place in the form of video-streaming, real-time lectures, networking, seminars or audio files. It takes place both online and offline. The Internet has made learning more individualized and adaptable to different learning styles (Shehu *et al.*, 2023). Learning can be more flexible, personalized, collaborative and more fun in digital classrooms (Joyne *et al.*, 2019). A digital classroom is a situation where ICT and internet facilities are used to provide additional learning opportunities as an extension of the physical classroom to enhance students learning (Singh, 2021). According to Taylor *et al.*, (2021), digital learning refers to the use of technology in instructional practices to enhance students' educational experience. This involves a diverse range of tools and methodologies. The influence of technology utilization on student results is contingent upon its incorporation within the educational setting. Consequently, it is crucial to recognize the correlation between students' digital competencies and their performance in digital learning environments (Hatos *et al.*, 2022). According to recent research conducted by Joyne *et al.*, (2019) and Fischer *et al.*, (2023), substantial evidence suggests that most students in the 21st century possess a high level of proficiency in technology.

Consequently, it is essential to effectively use this technological aptitude to provide optimal and uninterrupted learning experiences. The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the educational system has shown the need for the Nigerian educational sector to transform its methods of teaching and learning (Ojukwu *et al.*, 2021). According to Saavedra *et al.*, (2020), the alignment of instructors, students, and technology in e-learning holds promise for mitigating the longstanding issue of learning disparity, which has hindered global educational advancement.

The COVID-19 pandemic, along with its effects such as the closure of educational institutions, has emphasized the need for a comprehensive reevaluation of the conventional physical classroom in comparison to virtual classrooms in the post-COVID-19 era. During the height of the global pandemic in April 2020, an estimated 1.6 billion students across more than 190 countries experienced a lack of access to traditional face-to-face education (UNESCO, 2020a). According to a report by UNESCO, UNICEF, World Bank and OECD in October 2021, over 32% of nations globally have implemented either complete or partial closures of educational institutions. According to the findings of Munoz-Najar *et al.*, (2021), a significant proportion of countries in Sub-Saharan Africa, approximately 40%, did not implement any remote learning measures as of June 2021. This is even though these countries experienced complete or partial closures of schools for an average duration of one year. Consequently, a considerable number of children in these countries were deprived of educational instruction during this period. To effectively implement blended learning, students in the twenty-first century must possess the necessary abilities that will enable them to make the most of information and communication technology (ICT) resources as instruments for learning (UNESCO, 2020a). According to Onyebinama (2021), ICT skills include the proficiencies required by students to effectively use computers and IT equipment for a range of activities, including but not limited to accessing the Internet, composing written documents, using email services, developing presentations, and engaging in other related tasks. ICT abilities include a spectrum that spans from basic to intermediate and ultimately advanced levels. Anton-Sancho *et al.*, (2023) conducted a study in which they found that the COVID-19 pandemic resulted in a significant reliance on the use of ICT abilities for various activities, communication, and facilitating students' acquisition of many forms of knowledge. This shift towards learner-centered methods in using ICT is a worldwide phenomenon with methodological implications. Students who possess proficiency in ICT can effectively navigate ICT-based learning settings and use ICT tools to enhance the acquisition of knowledge and the cultivation of critical thinking abilities. Conversely, students who lack these competencies will face significant obstacles in these areas. According to Munoz-Najar *et al.*, (2021), there is evidence suggesting that some disadvantaged populations, such as females and students with impairments, may have a disproportionate impact and face an increased risk of falling behind in their e-learning endeavors (UNESCO, 2020b). In contrast, the study conducted by Shehu *et al.*, (2023) found that the use of information and communication technology (ICT) in educational settings resulted in enhanced academic performance across students, regardless of their gender.

Extensive research endeavors have been undertaken in Nigeria to use the field of ICT for educational purposes at different levels within the educational system. A case study was conducted by De Simone *et al.*, (2020) in Edo State to ascertain the prevailing ICT facilities accessible to pupils. The study focused on providing educational information and learning activities using mobile devices. The findings suggest that around 91% of the student population within the State could use mobile communication devices. The collaboration between Edo State, the World Bank, and Bridge International Academies during the COVID-19 epidemic resulted in the development of a comprehensive online learning platform called The Edo Basic Education Sector Transformation Programme (Edo-BEST@Home, Munoz-Najar & Oviawe, 2020). The programme exhibited transformative learning outcomes for a substantial number of children, exceeding 250,000, in over 800 public primary schools in Edo State, Nigeria. However, research reports from October 2020 to February 2021 suggest that merely 49 % of the overall secondary student population enrolled in the State, managed to utilize the mobile interactive quizzes. One of the problems encountered by students while interacting with Edo-BEST@Home's materials was the need to possess digital abilities to use the gadget effectively (Obaseki, 2021). According to the findings of Wu *et al.*, (2022), the efficacy of integrating the use of ICT in educational institutions may be contingent upon the digital proficiency of students. Studies (Siddiquah & Salim, 2017; Fidelis & Onyango, 2021; Ojukwu, *et al.*, 2021) showed that ICT facilities are unavailable or inadequate for learning, lack of ICT skills (Siddiquah & Salim, 2017; Onyebinama, 2021; Shehu *et al.*, 2023) and lack of integration or low usage of ICT in learning ((Munoz-Najar & Oviawe, 2020; Anton-Sancho *et al.*, 2023).

The College of Education system in Nigeria is one of the tripods of tertiary education and its primary role is to train professional teachers who will be awarded the minimum teaching qualification of Nigeria Certificate in Education. This certificate qualifies them to teach in primary, secondary and vocational schools. In recognition of the vital roles of teachers, the federal government in its National Policy on Education (FRN, 2016) and National Policy on Information and Communication Technologies in Education (FRN, 2019) emphasized the need to inculcate the use of ICT for teaching and learning purposes in its institutions. Some effort has been made by the government towards actualizing this by providing some

facilities, broadband, networking etc., but there is a need to determine human capacity development for effective and efficient utilization of ICT by teachers and students. Although studies have been carried out on ICT skills and competencies of teachers, there is a gap in information regards students, especially in Colleges of Education in Nigeria. Furthermore, based on the lessons learnt from COVID-19 experiences, how prepared and competent are the students in Nigerian Colleges of Education System in ICT skills for effective 21st-century post-COVID-19 learning?

Many students are admitted into tertiary institutions like Colleges of Education without academic skills for ICT learning. Even though they might be digital literates, they do not have adequate knowledge to use the resources available to them for proper learning. The COVID-19 pandemic and its fallouts which caused a worldwide disruption of activities in recent history, had already had a near-universal impact on learners around the world as drastic measures towards checking the spread of the deadly virus led to total lockdowns including educational institutions at all levels. Ensuring learning continued during this pandemic, ICT platforms were explored, requiring teachers to hold virtual classes. The Nigerian government has made efforts towards e-learning by providing certain ICT facilities in tertiary institutions. Moreso, most of these students possess Internet-ready mobile phones. This indicates that if all these resources are harnessed, lockdowns during pandemics should not affect teaching and learning. Research evidence has also shown a low level of ICT skills competence and usage among students in Nigeria. In some tertiary institutions in Nigeria, online learning has started taking place through recorded lectures and online platforms, but do Colleges of Education (COE) students have the requisite 21st-century ICT skills needed for successful, effective and quality post-COVID-19 learning?

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this research are to:

1. Ascertain the extent to which ICT facilities are available to students at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria.
2. Determine the level of ICT skills among students at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria.
3. Determine the ICT usage by students at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria for academic purposes.
4. Determine gender disparity among students in terms of their level of ICT skills at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following questions were raised to guide the conduct of this research:

1. To what extent are ICT facilities available to the students at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria?
2. What is the level of students ICT skills at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria?
3. What is the level of ICT usage for learning among students at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria?
4. Is there any difference between male and female students' ICT skills at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. **H₀₁**: There is no significant difference in the availability of ICT facilities at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria.
2. **H₀₂**: There is no significant difference in ICT skills obtained among students in Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria.
3. **H₀₃**: There is no significant difference in the level of ICT usage for learning by students in Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria.
4. **H₀₄**: There is no significant difference between male and female students' level of ICT skills at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria.

Methodology

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study to evaluate the Information and Communication Technology Skills of students for Post COVID-19 Learning at Colleges of Education in North-West, Nigeria. All of the students who were enrolled in the 2021/2022 academic session at three Federal Colleges of Education in North-West Nigeria, namely the Federal College of Education in Kano, the Federal College of Education in Katsina, and the Federal College of Education in Zaria, made up the population of the study. The Colleges were purposively used for the study because they have the same source of funding and extant administrative documents. A total of 384 (243 male & 141 female) students were randomly selected by balloting as sample size for the study in line with Krejcie & Morgan (1970).

The instrument used for data collection was a validated Student ICT Skills Assessment Questionnaire (SICTSAQ), adapted from the PISA 2021 ICT Framework (OECD, 2018). Split-half method was used to determine reliability and a

Cronbach value of 0.74 was obtained. The questionnaire has four sections, A, B, C and D. Section A deals with the biodata of the respondents. Section B, containing 10 items, deals with the extent of availability of ICT facilities. The items were five Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5, very available (5), moderately available (4), neutral (3), fairly available (2), and not available (1). Section C contained 20 items on the level of ICT skills of the students with a scale ranging from Highly skilled (5), moderately skilled (4), undecided (3), fairly skilled (2) and not skilled (1). Section D contained 12 items on the usage of ICT in learning with the responses ranging from always (5), often (4), sometimes (3), rarely (2) and never (1). The decision rule was 1-1.49 Not available or not skilled or not used, 1.50 -2.49 fairly available or fairly skilled or rarely used, 2.50 -3.49 moderately available or moderately skilled or sometimes used, 3.50 – 5.00 very available or highly skilled or always used respectively. Two Science Education and one Computer Education expert from Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria validated the instrument for the study. All validators' suggestions were effected to further improve the instruments. Fifty students from the population but not the selected sample were used for pilot testing. Split-half method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument. Cronbach was used to determine the coefficient value of 0.74 which made the instrument reliable for the study.

To get approval to conduct research among students at the sampled institutions, the researchers sought introduction letters from their home institutions to the Provosts of those Colleges. Over eight weeks, the researchers gave the surveys to the respondents assisted by research assistants recruited from each College. The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.0 was used to analyze the data. Mean, standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, t-test and ANOVA to test hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question One:

To what extent are ICT facilities available to the students at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria?

Table 1: Summary of Students Response on the Extent of Availability of ICT Facilities for Learning at COEs

S/N	Items	Mean	Std.Dev	Decision
1	Computers	4.12	1.28	Very Available
2	Digital Camera	3.17	1.41	Moderately Available
3	Digital Video Camera	2.99	1.41	Moderately Available
4	Overhead Projector	3.08	1.41	Moderately Available
5	Storage Facilities	3.32	1.46	Moderately Available
6	Mobile Handset	3.68	1.42	Very Available
7	Whiteboard	3.51	1.44	Very Available
8	Internet facilities	3.13	1.37	Moderately Available
9	Radio	3.14	1.51	Moderately Available
10	Television	3.04	1.57	Moderately Available
Cumulative Mean & Std.Dev		3.32	1.43	Moderately available

Results in Table 1 showed a cumulative mean score of 3.32 and a standard deviation value of 1.43 which indicate that ICT facilities are moderately available at each of the three Federal Colleges of Education located in the North-West region of Nigeria.

Research Question Two:

What is the level of students ICT skills at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria?

Table 2: Summary of Level of ICT Skills obtained by Students at COEs

S/N	Items	Mean	Std. dev.	Decision
1	Turning the Computer on and off	4.40	1.07	Moderately skilled
2	Opening and closing application programs	3.72	1.26	Moderately skilled
3	Using the Mouse to select and move items on the screen	3.76	1.27	Moderately skilled
4	Printing Out Document	3.41	1.38	Skilled
5	Saving and Storing File or Documents	3.55	1.41	Moderately skilled
6	Using word processing applications/packages to create new documents	3.35	1.38	Skilled
7	Using basic MS Word functions	3.44	1.34	Skilled

8	Using the toolbar for formatting documents by selecting font size and style	3.24	1.36	Skilled
9	Creating tables and Charts to display information within a document	3.27	1.37	Skilled
10	Creating a spreadsheet workbook/document	3.46	1.39	Skilled
11	Entering and processing data on Excel	3.49	1.36	Skilled
12	Creating and managing files and folders	3.44	1.32	Skilled
13	Copying, moving and locating stored files or folders	3.47	1.34	Skilled
14	Creating slides for a presentation using PowerPoint	3.29	1.37	Skilled
15	Connecting a mobile handset to a computer/printer	3.45	1.34	Skilled
16	Searching for information using search engines such as Google	3.54	1.38	Moderately skilled
17	Composing, attaching documents, sending and receiving e-mail	3.43	1.36	Skilled
18	Data Transfer from camera to computer	3.15	1.38	Skilled
19	Recording with a digital video camera	3.34	1.36	Skilled
20	Downloading/uploading files on the Internet	3.44	1.43	Skilled
Cumulative Mean & Std.Dev		3.48	1.34	Moderately skilled

The cumulative mean value of 3.48 and standard deviation of 1.48 presented in Table 2 revealed that students are moderately skilled.

Research Question Three:

What is the level of ICT usage for learning among students at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria?

Table 3: Summary of Responses on the Level of Students Usage of ICT Skills in Learning

S/N	Item	Mean	Std.Dev.	Decision
1	Using ICT to monitor and assess result	3.79	1.40	Often
2	Sharing electronic content with other students/teachers online	3.35	1.41	Sometimes
3	Write tests/examinations online	2.91	1.42	Sometimes
4	Using a digital video camera to record lessons	2.78	1.44	Sometimes
5	Using ICT to access online lessons via different Google Apps such as Google Classroom, Google Meet	2.90	1.47	Sometimes
6	Using ICT to access lessons on a real-time basis using Apps such as Zoom, Webinar/Webcast, Skype, Microsoft Teams	2.84	1.48	Sometimes
7	Using ICT to access online lessons via social media Apps such as WhatsApp, Telegram, Facebook, Instagram and Twitter	3.22	1.41	Sometimes
8	Using online video tools such as YouTube to learn	3.19	1.42	Sometimes
9	Using PowerPoint presentation for learning	3.07	1.45	Sometimes
10	Using an interactive whiteboard to learn a lesson	3.31	1.56	Sometimes
Cumulative Mean and Std.Dev		3.14	1.59	Moderately Used

The analysis of the level of students' use of ICT skills in learning shown in Table 3 revealed a cumulative mean value of 3.14 and a standard deviation of 1.59 which points to a moderate amount of use.

Research Question Four:

Is there any difference between male and female students' ICT skills at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria?

Table 4. Summary of Mean Scores of ICT Skills obtained by Male and Female Students at COEs

S/N	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Dev	Mean Difference
1	Male	243	3.57	1.27	

0.29

2 Female 141 3.28 1.23

The summary of means presented in Table 4 revealed a slight difference of 0.29 in favour of the male students. The significance of the difference will be determined in the related hypothesis.

H01:

There is no significant difference in the availability of ICT facilities at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria.

Table 5. One-Way Analysis of Variance of Students Response on Availability of ICT Facilities in COEs

S/N	Variables	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	df	f value	p-value	Decision
1	Between Groups	145.535	72.77	2			
2	Within Groups	6333.206	2.012	3147	36.16	.000	Significant
3	Total	6478.742		3149			

F(2, 3147), =36.16; p < 0.05

Table 5 indicate a significant difference between the three Colleges of Education in the North-West regions of Nigeria regarding the availability of ICT facilities ($p=000<0.05$). The null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the availability of ICT facilities at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria was consequently disproved.

H02:

There is no significant difference in ICT skills obtained among students in Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria.

Table 6. One-Way Analysis of Variance of COE Students Response on the Level of ICT Skills

S/N	Variables	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	df	f value	p value	Decision
1	Between Groups	51.403	25.701	2			
2	Within Groups	15648.185	1.917	8161	13.40	.000	Significant
3	Total	15699.587		8163			

F(2, 8161), =13.40; p < 0.05

One-way analysis of variance presented in Table 6 indicate that there is a significant difference in the level of ICT skills obtained by the COE students ($p=.000<0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the level of ICT skills acquired by students at Colleges of Education in the North West of Nigeria was rejected.

H03:

There is no significant difference in the level of ICT usage for learning by students in Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria.

Table 7. One-Way Analysis of Variance of COE Students' Response on the Level of ICT Usage for Learning

S/N	Variables	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	df	f value	p value	Decision
1	Between Groups	195.453	97.73	2			
2	Within Groups	8150.860	2.124	3837	46.00	.000	Significant
3	Total	8346.312		3839			

F(2, 3837), =46.00; p < 0.05

Table 7's One-way ANOVA revealed a statistically significant difference with $p =000<0.05$. The null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the level of ICT usage for learning by students in Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria was therefore rejected.

H04:

There is no significant difference between male and female students' level of ICT skills at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria.

Table 8: Summary of t-test scores on the level of ICT skills obtained among Male and Female Students in COEs

S/N	Gender	N	Mean	Std.Dev	Mean Diff	df	t value	p value	Decision
1	Male	243	3.57	1.27					

	0.29	382	1.99	.185	NS
2	Female	141	3.28	1.23	

Not Significant [t (382) = 1.99, p = .185 > 0.05].

Results in Table 8 revealed that the mean difference value of 0.29 was not statistically significant.

Discussion of Findings

According to the findings in Table 1, which showed a cumulative mean score of 3.32 and a standard deviation value of 1.43, indicate that ICT facilities are moderately available at each of the three Federal Colleges of Education located in the North-West region of Nigeria. The results of the corresponding variance analysis, provided in Table 5, indicate a significant difference between the three Colleges of Education in the North-West regions of Nigeria regarding the availability of ICT facilities ($p=000<0.05$). The null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the availability of ICT facilities at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria was consequently disproved. This conclusion is confirmed by the findings of Fidelis and Onyango (2021), who observed that insufficient technological innovation resources were accessible for teaching and learning in Tanzania. Furthermore, it was reported by students that the ICT facilities that are most easily available include computers, whiteboards, and mobile phones. In a study conducted by Ojukwu *et al.*, (2021), it was found that tertiary institutions in the state of Imo utilize various ICT tools for learning in the post-COVID-19 era. These tools include computers, whiteboards, smart boards, social media tools, Internet connectivity, projectors, computer-based learning software, audio and video tapes, CD-ROMs, local intranet/extranet systems, smartphones, digital cameras, scanners, and audio and video resources. The results align with the findings of Siddiquah and Salim (2017), which demonstrated that most higher education students in Pakistan have the means to use computers and access the Internet.

Table 2 provides data on the level of information and communication technology (ICT) skills achieved by students attending COEs in the North-West, Nigeria. The mean value of 3.48 and standard deviation of 1.48 revealed that students are moderately skilled. The results of this research are similar to those of Oguguo *et al.*, (2020), who found that undergraduate students at the University of Nigeria, Nsuka, have a moderate level of ICT skills. On the other hand, the conclusions of this research are contradicted by the findings of Siddiquah and Salim (2017), who discovered that students attending higher education institutions in Pakistan had a poor level of ICT skills. Table 6 presents the results of the one-way analysis of variance, which indicate that there is a significant difference in the level of ICT skills obtained by the COE students ($p=.000<0.05$). These results demonstrate that there is a substantial difference in the level of ICT Skills gained by the COE Students. Therefore, it is possible to conclude that the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the level of ICT skills acquired by students at Colleges of Education in the North West of Nigeria, was erroneous and should not be accepted.

Table 3 shows the results of an analysis of the level of students' use of ICT skills in learning. A cumulative mean value of 3.14 and a standard deviation of 1.59 point to a moderate amount of use (sometimes). The result contradicts what Omorobi *et al.*, (2021) found, which was that students had a high level of competency in information and communication technology skills. The corresponding Table 7's one-way ANOVA revealed a statistically significant difference, with a p-value of less than 0.05 ($p=000<0.05$). The null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the level of ICT usage for learning by students in Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria was therefore rejected. The results of an in-depth analysis of the factors suggest that the students make more use of video-based educational resources like YouTube ($p = 0.85$). According to Anton-Sancho *et al.*, (2023), one of the variables that may be identified as a barrier to students acquiring digital skills is the high cost of facilities for utilization.

A t-test analysis was conducted to assess the gender difference in mean scores attained by male and female COE Students regarding the degree of ICT abilities. Based on the findings presented in Table 8, the mean difference value of 0.29 was not statistically significant ($t = 1.99, P = .185 > 0.05$). This supports the findings of Oguguo *et al.*, (2020), who also observed that the ICT abilities of male and female students were not significantly different. The results that were obtained in this study contradict those found by Yalman *et al.*, (2016), who found that ICT skills obtained by male and female undergraduate education students in Turkey were substantially different regarding gender.

Conclusion

Findings from this study have shown a need for transformation of learning to continue when schools are closed due to any pandemic. COE students need to acquire the pre-requisite 21st-century digital skills needed to enhance learning. Most COE students in the North-West Zone, Nigeria possess basic ICT skills which require improvement for meaningful online/digital educational engagement/ learning. Therefore, it is imperative to clearly understand how COE students' progression and attainment of ICT skills can align with their curriculum, assessment and teacher training for both physical and

digital classrooms. The use of mobile technology can also be harnessed to enhance digital learning as the majority of the students have access to mobile phones.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

1. Students enrolled in the Colleges of Education in North-West, Nigeria are encouraged to enhance their proficiency in ICT skills.
2. COE students should endeavor to incorporate their abilities in ICT into their educational pursuits.
3. To boost students' competence, it is recommended that Lecturers at the Colleges of Education increase the frequency of learning activities in particular areas of need within the digital domain.
4. The provision of sufficient and appropriate infrastructure and ICT facilities inside and outside the school premises should be ensured by the Federal Government, the National Commission for Colleges of Education, and the Management of Colleges of Education, to enhance the learning process.

Acknowledgements

The authors deepest gratitude goes to the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) for the research grant. Also, the Management, Staff and Students of Federal Colleges of Education Kano, Katsina and Zaria are generously acknowledged for their invaluable cooperation and participation in the study.

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